

Predicting safety margins of equilibrium cycles: a surrogate model based on Graph Neural Network architecture with Attention layers

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ABSTRACT

Fuel management optimization is a non-linear combinatorial problem characterized by multiple constraints and objectives. This study focuses on the optimization of equilibrium cycles, an idealized set of conditions frequently used in the development of long-term fuel management strategies. Due to the high dimensionality of the problem and the computational expense associated with simulating equilibrium behavior, a surrogate modeling methodology is introduced to improve computational efficiency. The approach employs the PyTorch-Geometric (PyG) library and utilizes a Graph Neural Network (GNN) Transformer encoder to predict equilibrium cycle safety margins. By leveraging the inherent graph structure of equilibrium cycles, the proposed framework enables accurate safety margin prediction while substantially reducing computational time, thereby supporting faster and more scalable fuel management optimization.

Keywords: In-core Fuel Management, Evolutionary Strategies, Machine Learning, Transformers, GNN

1. INTRODUCTION

In-core fuel management optimization is a routine yet critical task for nuclear engineers, intended to enhance fuel economy while keeping reactor operation within established safety margins. Within this domain, two primary categories of optimization activities can be identified.

The first is cycle-to-cycle in-core fuel management optimization, which focuses on determining the optimal fuel loading configuration for each operational cycle. This process begins with a known inventory of fresh and partially burned fuel and utilizes real operational data [1]. This type of optimization is typically applied to operating power plants and is essential for maintaining performance and safety across successive cycles.

The second category is equilibrium cycle optimization, where the objective is to identify a fuel loading configuration that is repeated periodically. These activities are conducted to assess the long-term cost-effectiveness of various fuel management strategies. In the context of Pressurized Water Reactors (PWRs) [2], by repeatedly applying the same explicit fuel management scheme, the feed fuel composition and discharge conditions converge, exhibiting minimal variations across cycles. The inputs for this optimization problem are the fresh fuel composition and the specific fuel management scheme under consideration.

Interestingly, the equilibrium cycle optimization problem shares structural similarities with the well-known Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) and its extension to multiple agents - the Multiple Traveling Salesman Problem (mTSP) [3]. Both are combinatorial optimization problems, and the conceptual

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analogy lies in the reshuffling of fuel assemblies (FAs), which resembles multiple salesmen visiting sequences of cities. This analogy suggests that methods developed for solving the mTSP could be adapted for equilibrium cycle optimization. However, fuel management optimization is inherently a highly non-linear problem, subject to numerous operational and safety constraints. Therefore, while mTSP-inspired approaches offer a promising starting point, specialized techniques must be developed to effectively address the equilibrium cycle optimization problem.

Equilibrium cycle optimization problems can be subdivided into two distinct and complementary sub-problems: (i) identifying an effective search algorithm; (ii) reducing the computational burden of predicting the objective functions. The effectiveness of search algorithms for fuel management optimization has been extensively studied in the literature [4]. On the other hand, the development of accurate and efficient predicting algorithms remains a considerable challenge. For instance, in NRG's core optimization framework ROSA [5], the transition to equilibrium cycle is implicitly computed thanks to a fast 3D neutronic solver, compromising speed with accuracy in predictions. Concurrently, advances in machine learning have introduced promising methodologies for development of fast surrogate modeling in core optimization. These approaches have been extensively investigated to augment or replace conventional neutronic solvers [6], particularly in applications involving first-core and cycle-to-cycle optimization. However, only a limited number of studies have addressed equilibrium cycles directly [7], highlighting a gap in the current literature.

A methodology for constructing a data-driven surrogate model is introduced to estimate operational safety margins using machine learning. The approach uses the graph-like structure inherent in fuel management schemes, enabling efficient learning and generalization across configurations. This methodology aims to bridge the gap between computational feasibility and modeling fidelity.

This work has been conducted on a 990 Megawatt-thermal (MWth) 121-lattice elements Gen III+ PWR style Small Modular Reactor fueled with a modern 17x17 square lattice fuel design. In particular, using the Westinghouse core analysis package NEXUS/ANC9 [8], [9] with lattice data generated from the lattice code PARAGON [10], the neutronic performance of 20,000 fuel management configurations were evaluated. These configurations form the training, testing, and validation datasets for the surrogate model developed in this work.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Equilibrium cycle modeling

This study focuses on 36-month - 1080 Effective Full Power Days (EFPD) - equilibrium cycles, considering a scenario where 44 FA are replaced with fresh fuel at the beginning of each cycle. In addition, every three cycles, the central FA is replaced with fresh fuel.

The process began with the preparation of a comprehensive database of lattice cross sections, which served as input for full-core nodal calculations. Using the PARAGON lattice physics code, cross section data were generated for a range of fuel lattice configurations, varying both the enrichment levels and the number of gadolinia burnable absorber (BA) rods. Specifically, lattice designs were selected from existing Westinghouse databases that feature optimized pin layouts with respect to BA positioning.

This study was conducted without applying radial or axial enrichment grading, except for gadolinia-containing fuel pellets, where the enrichment was reduced by 40% relative to non-poisoned pellets. For BA rods, the 144-inch (≈ 366 cm) active core height included axial blankets: the top and bottom 6 inches (≈ 15 cm) were replaced with fuel pellets without BA. Equilibrium cycles were modeled by repeatedly applying explicit fuel management schemes until key performance indicators - namely power distributions and critical boron concentration (CBC) at Beginning of Cycle (BoC) and End of Cycle (EoC) - exhibited negligible variation across successive cycles. Due to the cycle-to-cycle asymmetries introduced by the periodic replacement of the central FA every three cycles, these indicators were observed

to stabilize after nine cycles. Consequently, the safety margins for Cycles 10 through 12 were investigated. In particular, the analysis focused on:

- The maximum value of the CBC and the average EoC CBC.
- The maximum value of the hot-channel power peaking factor (F_q), the enthalpy rise hot-channel factor (F_{dh}), and the axial power peaking factor (F_z).
- The absolute value of the power Axial Offset (AO).
- The minimum and maximum Moderator Temperature Coefficient (MTC).
- The Doppler Power Coefficient (DPC).
- The maximum rod-averaged burnup margins, evaluated as the ratio between axially averaged pin burnup and the local burnup limit.

These parameters also serve as the output targets for the surrogate model. In this study, CBC and BAs were the only mechanisms employed to control excess reactivity. All control rod banks were assumed to be fully withdrawn throughout the cycle, ensuring a consistent and simplified modeling framework.

The set of fuel management schemes was generated using a combination of random sampling and evolutionary strategies, with selection mechanisms based on configuration performances. Within this framework, up to three distinct fuel designs were selected for each configuration. To reduce the complexity of the optimization space while preserving physical realism, loading patterns were constrained to exhibit quadrant symmetry, with the additional flexibility of in-place FA rotation.

2.2. Surrogate modeling

The surrogate model developed for this work adopts the graph representation of the fuel management scheme as input parameter to predict the safety margins reported in the previous section. An example of a fuel management scheme and its corresponding graph is shown in Figure 1. The graph representation includes two distinct types of edges: bi-directional adjacency connections, shown in red, which represent the physical connectivity between nodes, and fuel reshuffling connections, shown in blue. Different weights are assigned to these edges to reflect their respective roles in the model. Each node is associated with a set of features that describe the FA composition, including nominal enrichment, the number of gadolinia rods, fuel residence time, and its equivalent position within the reactor core (node and quadrant). Positional information is encoded using sinusoidal embeddings [11], enabling the model to capture spatial relationships effectively.

The surrogate model was developed using supervised machine learning - a data-driven approach in which the model is trained to estimate safety margins corresponding to a given fuel management scheme graph. Furthermore, the model was designed to provide a confidence interval for each prediction, based on the assumption that the predicted values follow a normal distribution. The surrogate model was implemented using the Python libraries PyTorch [12] and PyTorch Geometric (PyG) [13], specifically developed to handle graph-like input data. To represent fuel management schemes as graph structures, the Python package *networkx* [14] was utilized, providing the input format required by the surrogate model. The model architecture is illustrated in Figure 2. As shown, the input graph is processed through a series of blocks before generating predictions for the safety margins. These predictions are represented by two vectors: one for the mean values of the assumed normal distributions (\mathbf{y}_{pred}), and another for their corresponding standard deviations (σ_{pred}).

Transformer Encoder and Feature Aggregation. The Transformer Encoder and Feature Aggregation blocks serve to convert the graph-structured input into a high-dimensional vector representation that captures the complex relationships inherent in the graph. To achieve this, the PyG implementation of the *TransformerConv* layer [15] was employed, a specialized Graph Neural Network (GNN) layer incorporating an attention mechanism. This layer is specifically designed to process both nodal features and edge attributes. Traditional Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) layers, commonly used in cycle-to-cycle surrogate modeling [6], lack the capability to represent nodal connectivity - an essen-

Figure 1. Representation of a fuel management scheme (left) and its corresponding graph (right). In the scheme, each node is associated with an assembly type and identifier, along with in-core residence time and rotation status. The rotation status is expressed using the cardinal coordinates of the quadrant to ensure an equivalent scheme without assembly rotation. Each color represents a specific FA as it transitions through its burnup stages, from fresh feed, 2nd-cycle, and 3rd-cycle positions. In the graph representation, blue arrows indicate edges corresponding to fuel reshuffling movements, while red arrows indicate edges representing physical connections between adjacent nodes. The central FA is highlighted to illustrate the stationarity of the assembly for three cycles before being replaced with a fresh one.

tial aspect when modeling fuel reshuffling. On the other hand, standard GNN layers typically do not differentiate between edge types, as they do not explicitly compute edge attributes. The integration of attention mechanisms has been shown to enhance generalization across various domains [11], making it a suitable choice for this application. In this architecture, the Transformer Encoder block consists of multiple *TransformerConv* layers with progressively increasing hidden feature dimensions, interleaved with normalization layers to enhance training stability. The Feature Aggregation block then completes the transformation by merging the nodal features using pooling operations that compute both the maximum and mean components. This results in a vector representation that encapsulates information about the specific fuel management scheme and the average feed fuel composition.

Dimensionality reduction. The encoded graph properties are subsequently processed through a series of multi-layer perceptrons (MLP) with ReLU activation functions and batch normalization. These hidden layers serve a dual purpose: reducing the dimensionality of the encoded graph representation and extracting non-linear features before passing them to the output layers.

Model output, Loss Function and Model Training. The model incorporates two output branches to enable uncertainty-aware predictions. Training is guided by the minimization of the batch-averaged Negative Log-Likelihood (NLL) loss, which encourages both accurate predictions and well-calibrated uncertainty estimates. For each output parameter, the NLL loss of the i -th fuel management is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NLL},i} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{y_{\text{true},i} - y_{\text{pred},i}}{\sigma_{\text{pred},i}} \right)^2 + \log(2\pi\sigma_{\text{pred},i}^2) \right] \quad (1)$$

During training, both the predicted mean ($y_{\text{pred},i}$) and standard deviation ($\sigma_{\text{pred},i}$) are updated simulta-

Figure 2. Model structure, where the roles of the different blocks have been highlighted. The input and output features in each layer has been highlighted.

neously. Since the model output parameters span several orders of magnitude, output standardization was applied to improve training efficiency. In this context, the Mean Squared Error (MSE) was adopted as an additional metric to monitor training performance on the standardized outputs. The dataset was partitioned into training (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%) subsets. Model parameters optimization was performed using the AdamW optimizer with a weight decay ($w = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$), complemented by L1 regularization ($\lambda_{\text{reg}} = 1.5 \times 10^{-5}$) to mitigate overfitting. A cosine annealing learning rate scheduler was employed to promote convergence and avoid local minima. Additionally, early stopping with checkpointing based on validation performance was implemented to enhance generalization and prevent overfitting.

3. RESULTS

Figure 3 summarizes the evolution of the NLL loss and MSE metric across the training, validation, and test sets, considering a standardized output. Notably, the training process was halted due to early stopping, triggered when the validation loss reached its minimum at epoch 193, indicating optimal generalization performance.

Regarding the NLL loss, the validation and test sets exhibit similar performance, whereas the training set achieves lower losses, suggesting potential overfitting. The use of cosine annealing in the LR scheduler proves beneficial: when the model begins to overfit, resetting the LR to its initial value enables further exploration of the parameter space, potentially discovering new local or global optima that improve generalization. For the MSE metric, the test set performs slightly better than the validation set and comparably to the training set, showing a somewhat different pattern than observed in the NLL loss. This suggests that the predicted uncertainties compensate for variations in mean accuracy between the validation and test sets. The slightly lower MSE for the test set in comparison to the validation set is likely due to sampling effects rather than a genuine performance difference.

Figure 4 summarizes the model predictions for the test and validation datasets, along with a table reporting the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) for all safety margins. For most quantities, the model effectively captures latent variables and produces outputs that closely follow theoretical normal distributions. Two notable exceptions are observed for the power peaking factors, F_q and F_z , likely due to the absence of a detailed axial fuel assembly description among the input parameters. In addition, the pairwise standardized error distributions exhibit notable correlations between Maximum CBC, EoC CBC, Minimum MTC and Maximum MTC. While a definitive interpretation of these relationships remains unclear, the observed trends suggest the presence

of dominant hidden neurons influencing the model's behavior. This may indicate that, in evaluating these quantities, the model prioritizes the average feed composition over the specific fuel management scheme.

The full dataset was generated using evolutionary search algorithms, with selection criteria based on configuration performance. As a result, most output values are concentrated within narrow regions of the performance space. This is a direct consequence of the selection mechanism: poorly performing configurations were rarely retained or used to generate new candidates. Within these dense regions, the model exhibits improved confidence, suggesting that the data generation process has introduced a bias in the model's predictive capabilities.

Figure 3. History of loss function (NLL, left) and test metric (MSE, right) for training, validation, and test dataset.

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ACTIVITIES

In this work, the underlying graph structure of equilibrium cycles is shown to be exploitable for developing a surrogate model capable of fast computation of safety parameters, reducing computational time from four hours to tens of milliseconds per configuration. For most parameters, the surrogate model shows good performance, including predictive uncertainties that explain the residuals, indicating suitability for future optimization studies. For axially dependent quantities, the limited predictive performance suggests that incorporating an axial fuel-assembly (FA) description into the input graph could provide improvements. Future activities on equilibrium cycles will include axial FA composition optimization, modeled under fixed boron trajectories to reflect realistic control strategies, thereby enabling the inclusion of safety parameters related to safe-shutdown conditions, such as shutdown margins.

Additionally, this study employed basic model optimization techniques. Future research will focus on implementing more advanced optimization strategies to refine model hyperparameters and provide a detailed comparison with alternative architectures.

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Figure 4. Output predictions for the test and validation datasets. Each column corresponds to a different output quantity. From top to bottom: (i) true values (red dashed lines) versus predicted values, with uncertainties shown as gray error bars; (ii) distributions of standardized errors, along with the theoretical Gaussian distribution ($\mu = 0, \sigma = 1$); (iii) pairwise standardized error distributions for combinations of quantities. In (i) and (iii), colors represent data point density, with darker shades indicating sparsely populated regions. At the top right corner, for each safety margin, it is shown a table summarizing the mean value of the distributions, the RMSE and the MAPE of the predictions.